

Management of Patients with Acute Drug Poisoning in the Context of Emergency Medical Services

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Abstract

The article provides a definition of acute drug poisoning, presents an updated classification of this type of poisoning, and describes the main tactical actions of an emergency medical physician when identifying a patient with suspected acute drug poisoning. Special attention is given to analyzing the causes behind the increasing incidence of drug poisonings at the present stage.

Keywords: drug poisoning, classification of poisonings, suicidal poisoning, toxicological situation, toxicological diagnosis, emergency medical care.

Introduction

This paper examines cases of acute poisoning based on the effects of toxic doses of pharmaceutical drugs on the human body.

Drug poisoning is a disease of chemical etiology that develops when medicinal substances enter the body in a dose exceeding the therapeutic level and capable of causing disruption of vital functions and posing a threat to the patient's life [1,2].

The relevance of the problem is обусловлена (justified by) the expansion of the pharmaceutical market, the accessibility of medications, and the increasing number of both accidental and intentional poisonings [3].

Aim of the Study

The aim of this work is a comprehensive analysis of the danger posed to the human body by toxic doses of medicinal drugs, arising from both accidental and intentional превышения (exceedances) of therapeutic doses.

Research Methodology

The study is of a review-analytical nature and is based on the analysis of data from international clinical toxicology guidelines, recommendations of the World Health Organization, as well as contemporary English-language publications (2015–2024) devoted to the problem of acute drug poisoning and the provision of emergency medical care.

Results and Discussion

Drug poisonings occur in all age groups and occupy a significant place in the structure of emergency medical service calls [4].

The most common causes of drug poisonings are psycho-emotional factors (family conflicts, unrequited love, stressful situations), chronic and incurable diseases, as well as socio-economic problems [5].

Classification of Drug Poisonings

The classification of drug poisonings has not only theoretical but also practical significance, as it allows an emergency physician to quickly determine diagnostic priorities, the scope of urgent interventions, and the need to involve related specialists.

The presented classification is the author's interpretation, developed with consideration of the practical tasks of the prehospital stage of emergency medical care.

By origin:

1. Intentional:
 - a) suicidal;
 - b) criminal.
2. Accidental (erroneous):
 - a) household-related;
 - b) medical (iatrogenic), arising from incorrect drug administration or improper dosing.
3. Exploratory, imitative (more common in children and adolescents).

By number and type of drug:

- poisoning with a single drug;
- combined poisoning ("drug mixtures").

By number of affected individuals:

- isolated cases;
- group cases.

By diagnostic certainty:

- confirmed poisoning;
- suspected poisoning.

By severity:

- mild;
- moderate;
- severe.

By route of administration:

- oral;
- parenteral;
- rectal, vaginal, via the external auditory canal;
- intranasal (for example, use of vasoconstrictive drops in children).

Special Forms of Poisoning

Suicidal drug poisonings are carried out with the intent of self-harm by individuals with mental disorders or those in a state of acute psycho-emotional stress. The fact of poisoning is often concealed from others and medical personnel [6].

Combined poisonings develop as a result of the simultaneous exposure to medications and other toxic substances, particularly alcohol, which significantly aggravates the clinical course [7].

Pediatric drug poisonings are usually associated with imitative behavior and the mistaken perception of medications as food products or vitamins [8].

Periods of Poisoning Course

1. **Latent (hidden) period** – from the moment the toxic substance enters the body to the appearance of the first symptoms.
2. **Period of resorptive action** – from the onset of the first signs to the development of a full clinical picture.
3. **Period of maximal resorptive action** – symptoms of respiratory and cardiovascular failure, cerebral edema, and convulsive syndrome predominate.
4. **Recovery period.**

The relationship between the period of poisoning and the scope and priorities of medical interventions at the prehospital stage is of fundamental importance for the tactics of the emergency medical physician. The systematization of these tasks is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Periods of Acute Drug Poisoning and Priority Tasks of the Emergency Medical Physician

Period of poisoning	Clinical characteristics of the period	Main tasks of the emergency medical physician
Latent (hidden)	Absence or minimal symptoms; the patient may deny drug intake	Identification of toxicological history; assessment of the toxicological situation; search for medication packaging; prevention of further absorption
Period of resorptive action	Appearance of initial clinical manifestations of intoxication, progression of symptoms	Early clinical diagnosis; syndromic analysis; initiation of detoxification measures; monitoring of vital functions
Period of maximal resorptive action	Full clinical picture; respiratory and cardiovascular failure, seizures, coma	Maintenance of airway patency; intensive symptomatic therapy; antidote therapy (if indicated); urgent hospitalization
Recovery period	Regression of symptoms, stabilization of condition	Monitoring of vital functions; assessment of complications; ensuring continuity of treatment at the hospital stage

Seeking medical care during periods 1–2 is considered timely, while in period 3 it is regarded as delayed.

Tactics of the Emergency Medical Physician

Modern international approaches to the management of patients with acute drug poisoning emphasize the key role of the prehospital stage, during which timely identification of the toxic agent, syndromic analysis, and early initiation of treatment significantly influence the outcome of the disease [2,9,10].

The tactics of the emergency medical physician are based on the assessment of the toxicological situation, analysis of medical history, and clinical presentation. Inspection of the scene, search for medication packaging and ampoules, as well as interviewing relatives and witnesses are of great importance.

If identification of the toxic agent is not possible, a preliminary diagnosis of poisoning by an unknown substance is established, with the immediate initiation of syndrome-oriented treatment.

Prehospital Medical Care and Treatment in Acute Drug Poisoning

The prehospital stage of emergency medical care in acute drug poisoning is crucial for the prognosis, as it is within the first hours after ingestion of a toxic dose that it is possible to prevent further absorption of the toxic agent, correct life-threatening disturbances, and reduce the incidence of severe complications. The main goal of prehospital treatment is stabilization of vital functions, early initiation of detoxification measures, and timely routing of the patient to a specialized hospital.

Algorithm of Primary Medical Care at the Prehospital Stage

The tactics of an emergency medical physician in suspected acute drug poisoning should be algorithmic in nature and based on the principles of priority assessment and correction of vital functions.

1. **Airway management (A – airway).**
Assessment of the level of consciousness is carried out using the Glasgow Coma Scale. In cases of impaired consciousness, suppression of protective reflexes, or risk of aspiration, airway patency is ensured using airway adjuncts, head positioning, and, if necessary, tracheal intubation.
2. **Assessment and support of breathing (B – breathing).**
Pulse oximetry is indicated in all patients with suspected drug poisoning. In cases of respiratory insufficiency, oxygen therapy is administered; in respiratory depression, assisted or mechanical ventilation is provided. Particular attention is given to patients exposed to sedatives, opioids, and psychotropic drugs.
3. **Circulation support (C – circulation).**
Monitoring of blood pressure, heart rate, and electrocardiogram is mandatory. Venous access is established, and infusion therapy with crystalloid solutions is administered to correct hypotension and prevent shock. In life-threatening arrhythmias, urgent correction is performed in accordance with current protocols.
4. **Neurological assessment (D – disability).**
Evaluation includes the level of consciousness, pupillary responses, presence of seizures, and focal neurological symptoms. Seizures require immediate pharmacological management to prevent hypoxia and secondary brain injury.

Detoxification Measures at the Prehospital Stage

Early detoxification measures are aimed at reducing the entry of the toxic substance into the systemic circulation and should be carried out taking into account the time elapsed since ingestion, the patient's clinical condition, and the presumed pharmacological properties of the toxic agent.

Gastric lavage may be considered within the first hours after ingestion of a potentially dangerous dose of a drug, provided that consciousness is preserved or the airway is protected. Activated charcoal is used as an adsorbent in most oral drug poisonings, except for substances not amenable to adsorption. The administration of enterosorbents at the prehospital stage is most effective in the early period of poisoning.

It should be emphasized that detoxification measures must not delay the stabilization of vital functions and the implementation of intensive care measures.

Antidote and Symptomatic Therapy

Antidote therapy at the prehospital stage is administered strictly according to indications and when there is a high probability of intoxication with a specific class of drugs. The use of antidotes requires clinical justification and assessment of the risk–benefit ratio. Empirical use of antidotes in cases of an unidentified toxic agent should be limited to situations where the expected benefit outweighs the potential risk.

Symptomatic therapy is aimed at correcting the leading clinical syndromes—respiratory failure, seizures, hemodynamic disturbances, hyperthermia, and psychomotor agitation. This syndrome-

oriented approach allows effective treatment even in the absence of precise identification of the toxic substance.

Table 2. Main Clinical Syndromes in Acute Drug Poisoning and Emergency Physician Tactics at the Prehospital Stage

Clinical syndrome	Main clinical manifestations	Priority actions of the emergency physician
Depressed consciousness (stupor, coma)	Decreased level of consciousness, absence of response to painful stimuli, risk of aspiration	Glasgow Coma Scale assessment; airway management; oxygen therapy; aspiration prevention; monitoring of vital functions; urgent hospitalization
Respiratory failure	Bradypnea, tachypnea, decreased SpO ₂ , cyanosis	Assessment of respiration and oxygen saturation; oxygen administration; in case of respiratory depression—ventilatory support; monitoring of gas exchange; preparation for intubation if deterioration occurs
Cardiovascular failure	Arterial hypotension, tachycardia or bradycardia, signs of shock	Monitoring of blood pressure and ECG; venous access; infusion therapy; correction of hemodynamic disturbances; urgent transport
Cardiac arrhythmias	Extrasystoles, tachyarrhythmias, bradycardia, prolongation of ECG intervals	Continuous ECG monitoring; correction of life-threatening arrhythmias according to protocols; discontinuation of potentially cardiotoxic drugs
Seizure syndrome	Generalized or focal seizures, postictal state	Immediate seizure control; airway management; oxygen therapy; prevention of hypoxia and injuries; urgent hospitalization
Psychomotor agitation	Aggression, disorientation, hallucinations, anxiety	Ensuring safety of the patient and staff; sedative therapy as indicated; monitoring of consciousness and respiration; exclusion of hypoxia and hypoglycemia
Anticholinergic syndrome	Dry skin and mucous membranes, mydriasis, tachycardia, hyperthermia, agitation	Symptomatic therapy; temperature control; hemodynamic monitoring; transport to a toxicology unit
Opioid syndrome	Miosis, respiratory depression, coma	Airway control; ventilatory support; antidote therapy if indicated; monitoring of vital functions
Hypoglycemic syndrome	Sweating, tremor, impaired consciousness, seizures	Rapid glucose assessment; immediate correction of hypoglycemia; monitoring of consciousness; hospitalization
Combined drug poisoning	Polymorphic clinical picture, rapid deterioration	Syndrome-oriented therapy; priority on stabilization of vital functions; avoidance of narrowly targeted treatment; urgent hospitalization

The presented table reflects a syndrome-oriented approach to emergency medical care for drug poisonings at the prehospital stage and allows emergency physicians to make well-founded tactical decisions even in the absence of precise identification of the toxic agent.

Indications for Emergency Hospitalization

All patients with suspected moderate to severe drug poisoning are subject to mandatory hospitalization. Absolute indications for urgent transport to a specialized toxicology unit include:

- impaired consciousness;
- seizure syndrome;
- respiratory and cardiovascular failure;
- suspected ingestion of potentially lethal doses of drugs;
- combined drug poisonings.

In cases of suicidal poisoning, hospitalization is indicated regardless of the clinical severity, with mandatory subsequent psychiatric evaluation.

Role of the Prehospital Stage in Outcomes of Drug Poisoning

Thus, the prehospital stage of treatment of acute drug poisoning represents a key component of the emergency medical care system. Timely stabilization of vital functions, early initiation of detoxification, and the use of a syndrome-oriented approach significantly reduce mortality and the incidence of severe complications, and ensure continuity of care between the prehospital and hospital stages.

Causes of the Increase in Drug Poisoning

The increase in the number of drug poisonings is considered in the international literature as a consequence of a combination of pharmacological accessibility, social stress, and insufficient pharmacological literacy of the population, which is confirmed by epidemiological studies [3,11].

Objective reasons for the increased frequency of drug poisonings include:

- ease of implementing poisoning as a method;
- aggressive advertising of medications;
- affordability of drugs;
- over-the-counter availability of many medications;
- extensive pharmacy networks;
- low level of pharmacological literacy among the population;
- availability of medications in households and everyday environments.

Conclusions

1. Acute drug poisonings remain one of the most significant reasons for seeking emergency medical care at the prehospital stage.
2. The effectiveness of patient management largely depends on the physician's toxicological reasoning, including assessment of the toxicological situation, analysis of medical history, and a syndromic approach.
3. Accessibility of medications and low public awareness are key factors in the increase of drug poisonings.
4. Prevention and reduction of the incidence of these conditions require a comprehensive approach involving the medical community, healthcare systems, and legislative bodies.

Practical Significance

The provisions presented in this work may be used in the practical activities of emergency physicians, general practitioners, and medical interns to improve the quality of prehospital diagnosis and timely routing of patients with suspected drug poisoning.

Study Limitations

The work does not include a quantitative analysis of clinical observations and is primarily focused on the prehospital stage of medical care, which determines the review nature of the conclusions.

Prospects for Further Research

A promising direction is the development of unified algorithms for the management of patients with drug poisoning and the improvement of pharmacological literacy among the population.

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